

ISic3650

I.Sicily inscription 3650

Language

Latin

Type

funerary (?)

Material

breccia (local)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

contrada Muschigghia, sporadic find

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, San Marco d'Alunzio, Museo della cultura e
delle Arti Figurative Bizantine e Normanne, inventory 30

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3650. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI

edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388904>